

Role of Supply Chain Practices on Performance of Cement Manufacturing Firms in Kenya

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Abstract:

The main aim of the study was to determine the role of cost management on the performance of Cement Manufacturing firms, examine the role IT integration on performance of Cement Manufacturing firms in Kenya, to find out the extent to which top management supply support affect performance of Cement Manufacturing firms in Kenya and to find out the effect of lead-time on performance of Cement Manufacturing firms in Kenya. A descriptive research design was used. The target population of the study was Managers or equivalent from Six (6) departments that are Procurement, finance, legal, stores, human resource, and quality control because they are directly concerned with the supply chain. The sample size was 83 respondents from a target population of 500. The study adopted the use of a questionnaire as the main research instrument. The study adopted both quantitative and qualitative approaches, implying that both descriptive statistics and inferential statistics were employed. Quantitative data collected from the questionnaire were analyzed statistically using the Statistical Package for Social Scientist (SPSS version 24). The study tested the significance level of each independent variable against the dependent variable at a 95% confidence level using ANOVA, Correlation and regression techniques. The results revealed that cost management has no significant effect on the performance of cement manufacturing firms. However, through IT firms can manage suppliers information in a more effective and efficient manner. Therefore, IT needs to be used to select suppliers and facilitate interaction with suppliers electronically. Finally, firms have to work collaboratively to serve the customers.

Keywords: cost management, performance, Manufacturing, IT, manufacturing firms

Introduction

Supply chain practices emerged during the early 20th Century in Japan (Salawati et al., 2014). Excessive demand for parts of goods after World War I urged many companies to utilize suppliers following the temporary increase in productions. In the 1960s and '70s Supply chain practices were characterized by an adversarial, arm's -length approach suiting price oriented buying. At the beginning of the '90s, Supply chain practices required an even greater degree of interaction due to the added need for product innovation and cooperation in technological developments, and this high level of interaction is termed partnership (Arani et al., 2016).

However, many organizations are now moving towards more cooperative Supply chain practices with suppliers (Zhao & Wang, (2012). Firms compete in head-to-head battles for market share and position with other organizations in their competitive sets. Here suppliers are often treated in an adversarial manner by buyers, as the relationship between buyers and suppliers are viewed in a win-lose situation (Cheng and Wu, 2015). It is imperative, therefore for firms to appreciate that supply chain relationships are not simple to cultivate and maintain collaborative efforts. The Supply chain practices should be for a strategic subset of suppliers and customers of the supply chain. However, many forward-looking firms have found it more effective to work collaboratively with their suppliers to serve the ultimate customer. Terms such as alliances, partnerships, and collaborations have been used to describe these new buyer-supplier relationships (Sinha and Sarmah, 2007). Recent trends to buy instead of make, to outsource instead of continuing to make, to improve quality, to lower inventories, to integrate supplier and purchaser systems and to create cooperative relations such as partnerships have underlined the need for outstanding performance, and that calls for negotiation. For good supplier

relationship management, the members of the internal team have to deal directly with their appropriate counterparts on the supplier side (Van der Vaart, & van Donk, 2008).

Effective performance through the use of supply chain practices can lead to a reduction in cost, resulting in significant saving. A potential 6% saving on total cost through effective supply chain practices is achievable (World Bank, 2016). Today, it is commonly accepted that the cost of holding stock to a business is between 4% and 10% on top of the stock's value (PPOA, 2005). Cement Manufacturing firms in Kenya are characterized by elongated or overextended chains retailers (buyers/agents) which, in turn, mean long chains of transactions between chain members and consumers (Musa, 2011). World bank, (2016) showed that leading firms in Kenya are faced with problems of wrong forecasting due to an unavailability of enough supply chain practices. In 2014 all cement manufacturing firms were affected by poor supply chain practices related cases leading to low performance (NSE, 2015). This caused erratic deliveries, late deliveries and inflexibility hence affecting customer satisfaction within their downstream chain (Sila et al., 2016). Customers are concerned with the availability of the product and the ability of the firms to meet their needs timely (Gichuru et al., 2015). Among all the opportunities for savings, the Supply Chain & Logistics area is covering a wide range of possibilities since the supply chain accounts for 80% of the product costs Lwika, (2013).

Unavailability of integrated supply chain practices has affected performance at Portland cement hence reduced profits in the downstream chain hence leading to loss of chain profits (Okanda et al., 2016). There are few local studies done on establishing the effect of effective supply chain practices in enhancing the performance of commercial firms in Kenya. There are studies done on the adoption of supply chain practices by the public sector in the developed world. Thus the need to validate these in the context of the developing countries and in specific the cement manufacturing sector in the developing countries since the implementation of supply chain practices will adversely affect performance positively in terms of increasing the effectiveness and efficiency in the cement manufacturing sector.

Cement companies attain significant savings from effective supply chain practices, which amount between 40%-45% of total costs (Okello & Were, 2014). Effective supply chain practices can lead to a reduction in cost, resulting in significant saving. A potential 7% saving on total cost through effective inventory is achievable (Moinzadeh, 2011). Indeed, for many cement manufacturing firms inventory costs account for over 50 % of total production costs (Chen et al., 2014). Today, it is commonly accepted that the cost of inventory to a business is between 4% and 15% on top of the stock's value (PPOA, 2005). Cement Manufacturing firms in Kenya are characterized by elongated or overextended chains retailers (buyers/agents) which, in turn, mean long chains of transactions between chain members and consumers (Ouyang et al., 2017). (World Bank, 2016) showed that leading cement manufacturing firms in Kenya are faced with problems of wrong forecasting due to an unavailability of enough supply chain practices data. In 2012 Athi River mining was affected by poor supply chain practices related cases leading to low performance (NSE, 2014). This caused erratic deliveries in these firms, late deliveries and inflexibility hence affecting customer satisfaction within their downstream chain (Kimani, 2013). Customers are concerned with the availability of the product and the ability of the firms to meet their needs timely (Gunasekaran, 2011). Thus the study focuses on the role of supply chain practices on performance in cement manufacturing sector in Kenya with reference to Portland Cement Ltd. These previous studies did not address the Cement Manufacturing sector, and it is against this backdrop that this study was undertaken to look into the role of Supply Chain practices on performance of Cement Manufacturing firms in Kenya

Theoretical Review

The idea that transactions form the basis of an economic thinking was introduced by the institutional economist John R. Commons (1931). Transaction cost economics (TCE) is one of the most influential theories on inter-

firm collaboration. TCE suggests that a firm organize its cross organizational activities to minimize production costs within the firm and transaction costs within markets. TCE thinks that system users can reduce transaction costs, e.g., monitoring costs by specific asset investments, which diminish opportunistic behaviors (Deuermeyer & Schwarz, 2011).

De Treville et al., (2004) identify markets and hierarchies as two modes of organizing. Collaboration emerges as the third alternative. Supply chain practices help prevent the problems arising from both markets and hierarchies. It helps firms reduce the opportunism and monitoring costs that are inbuilt in market transactions through process integration and mutual trust, thus reduce the probability that partners behave opportunistically. A supply chain practice also helps firms avoid internalizing an activity that they do not excel (Eroglu & Hofer, 2011).

In effect to SRM systems, Ferreira, (2009) stated that adopting TCE theory in today's integrated supply chains which require collaboration at many levels and from various functions, executives are increasingly looking for innovative ways to leverage existing and new supplier relationships for their expansionary pursuit. SRM is one approach to connect the different interests both within the organization and with the extended supply chain. SRM identifies and engages the right stakeholders to create ownership of the relationship, drive effective communication and align strategic objectives. The result is a foundation for continuous efficiency improvements, such as cost management, risk mitigation or improved go-to-market times just as well as the improved potential for disruptive innovation.

The use of information technology (IT) has facilitated the reduction of coordination costs, which has been extensively documented in the literature (Forsgren and Johanson, 2002). For example, electronic marketplaces facilitated through IT, reduce the cost of searching for obtaining information about product offerings and prices (Forsgren and Johanson, 2002). Also, collaboration facilitated by information sharing can lower transaction costs (in particular coordination costs) as companies can thereby reduce supply chain uncertainty and thus the cost of contracting. This can be explained with an example: If a supplier is unable to predict the price of its product inputs accurately, it will be reluctant to enter into a contract, which locks it into a fixed price for an extended period of time (Gallego and O'zer, 2001).

The unified theory of acceptance and use of technology (UTAUT) is a technology acceptance model formulated by Chen and others in user acceptance of The IT towards a unified view. UTAUT aims to explain user intentions to use IT and subsequent usage behavior (Chen, 2014). The theory holds that four key constructs: performance expectancy, effort expectancy, social influence and facilitating conditions; being the first three direct determinants of usage intention and behavior, and the fourth a direct determinant of user behavior (Cox et al. 2004).

Chia, (2012) defined performance expectancy as the degree to which using a technology will provide benefits to consumers in performing certain activities; effort expectancy is the degree of ease associated with consumers use of technology; social influence is the extent to which consumers perceive that important others (e.g., family and friends) believe they should use a particular technology; and facilitating conditions refer to consumers perceptions of the resources and support available to perform a behavior.

In effect to SRM dimensions, Baiman & Rajan, (2012) argued that gradual increments of information sharing produce a positive increase in the local and global performance of the service supply chain. IT fosters the integration of business processes across the supply chain by facilitating the information flows, which is necessary for coordinating a business activity. Dubois, (2007) indicated that IT is focused mainly on acquiring and sharing information in order to create knowledge for the different actors involved that are using this distributed knowledge base. Many of the characteristics of IT seem to be just the right answer for a successful

Supply Chain Management strategy. Inter-company integration and coordination via IT, therefore, has become a key to improved performance

Review of Literature.

Costs management

Accordingly, any good procurement systems today are designed to greatly reduce the time and effort required to complete purchasing transactions by eliminating traditional paper chain of requisitions, approvals, receiving and payment reconciliation. The key features of most of these approaches enable users to find an item in an electronic catalog, create a requisition, have the order requisition routed for approval if necessary, create and transmit the order to vendors, and (in varying degrees) help to automate the payment and invoicing process (Axsater, 2013). One of the most important and beneficial effects of an e-procurement framework is that for the first time, business information systems are well integrated that they can provide an organization with the key tool cost data that allows them to make considered decisions on purchases, discount requirements and supplier partnerships (Baiman & Rajan, 2012). In many ways, it is only now that the internet and advanced software systems make it possible to capture accurate and timely information on every purchase, that companies can analyze complex buying patterns and make truly informed decisions on strategic sourcing option (Dubois, 2007).

The value of cost management adoption is defined as the benefit over costs of implementing. E-procurement adoption is justified only when the perceived benefit is large enough to cover the cost. The high cost of initial investment associated with the required infrastructure and training of personnel, quantifying the return on investment often becomes a barrier to state corporations (Baiman & Rajan, 2012).

Cost management is the process of collaborating with suppliers to improve their processes and product capabilities to minimize incurring more Krause et al. (2007). In the literature Krause et al. (2007) the concept of cost management is advocated as a means to transfer knowledge between the firm and its suppliers. Visiting suppliers is good for your knowledge. Firms should not only let the supplier deliver the products but must also know what more or else he can make the right products (Bergman & Klefsjo, 2010). In long-term relationships, it would be important to consider not just the current supplier capabilities, but also their potential capabilities. The concept of cost management was especially relevant to my research because it is a form of supplier relationship which assumes trust and reciprocity in information exchange (Handfield et al., 2000).

According to Clemons (2013), cost management is composed of related processes; assess the supplier's readiness for change, build commitment through collaboration, implement system-wide changes, transition out of the supplier's organization, establish follow-up and recognition procedures. Handfield et al. (2000), proposed a process map for cost management : such as identify critical commodities, identify critical suppliers, form a cross-functional team, meet with supplier's top management, identify key projects, define details of the agreement, monitor status and modify strategies. Strategic planning and risk definition, engagement, collaboration, and project management, process and controls, training and facilitation and continuous improvement and Surveillance (Handfield et al., 2000).

Cost management is an effort of a buying firm to increase the performance and capabilities of the supplier and meet the buying firm's supply needs (Krause et al., 2007). Due to long term strategic benefits from cost management , major global entities have implemented supplier development programs to support suppliers. Most of them have resulted in product quality improvement and reduction of cost (Krause et al., 2007). In view of this fact, the performance of suppliers has a significant effect on many production dimensions of the firm such as delivery and quality (Krause et al., 2007). Cement Manufacturing and service companies are trying to

work effectively with suppliers through sharing information, technical knowledge and schedules of production (Cox et al., 2004).

Basic activities require limited buying firm's involvement and are likely to hold a low implementation complexity (Baiman & Rajan, 2012). These include supplier evaluation and feedback, sourcing from a limited number of suppliers, parts standardization and supplier qualification. Moderate activities refer to those demanding moderate levels of buyer's involvement characterized by visiting suppliers to assess their facilities, recognizing and rewarding supplier improvements, collaboration with suppliers in terms of components improvement and supplier certification (Tsiakis et al., 2011). Advanced activities call for more resources to be allocated which is caused by high levels of buying the firm's involvement and implementation complexity (Tsiakis et al., 2011). Activities here consist of personnel training, new product development supplier involvement and sharing of vital data by the supplier, including financial, cost and quality related data.

According to Clemons, cost management programs can be either results or process-oriented. Results-oriented programs focus on solving specific problems for suppliers and normally involve step-by-step changes relating to suppliers' costs, quality and delivery (Clemons et al. 2013). Three characteristics of results oriented supplier development identified: the process is standardized and buyer-driven, the changes made are primarily technical, and the process is of short duration and requires limited follow-up. Process-oriented programs focus on increasing the supplier's ability to make production improvements without hands-on assistance from the buyer. This requires the supplier to learn the problem solving techniques required for continuous improvements (Clemons et al. 2013).

IT Integration

IT Integration considered an operational imperative in today's competitive environment, it is also a growth area and one of the key issues purchasing, and supply executives need to face now and in the near future (Kros et al., 2006). Although forecasts on the use of Technology have been downgraded with the burst of the internet bubble in 2011 (Kros et al., 2006), statistics still show an increased growth in the use of technology, for example a recent survey indicated that Technology of direct goods is now exceeding that of indirect goods (Sahin & Robinson, 2012). Reason for the continued growth in e-procurement use is due to the significant benefits both supplier and buyer organizations achieve through its use. Benefits include; lower transaction costs, lower staffing requirements, shorter procurement cycles, reduced inventory levels, a higher degree of transparency and increased communication between supplier and buyer organizations (Kros et al., 2006). Yet, for all the benefits outlined there are many organizations that are taking a 'wait and see' approach to the implementation of e-procurement technologies (Kros et al., 2006).

According to (Eroglu & Hofer, 2011), electronic procurement is the business-to-business purchase and sale of supplies and services through the internet, as well as other information and networking systems, such as EDI and ERP. As an important part of many business sites, e-procurement is sometimes referred to by other terms, such as supplier exchange. Typically, e-procurement websites allow qualified and registered users to look for buyers or sellers of goods and services.

Information technology and in particular the Internet, have played a fundamental role in helping companies reach the goals of supply chain integration. The Internet can change the role and type of relationships between the various players, creating new value networks and developing a new business model (Lambert & Cooper, 2016). These systems must fit within the organizational requirements of the supply chain/network members, or else the overall acceptance may not be adequate for the system's use (Gallego and O'zer, 2001).

Information systems, in particular, have contributed to the establishing of Supply chain management systems which link suppliers to the buyer organization promoting supplier intimacy (Topan et al., 2012). It has also led to the application of the Internet in the application of Electronic data exchange systems. The Internet has given companies even greater tools for tightly orchestrating relationships across the entire supply chain and creating strategic partnerships and operational linkages with a dynamic web of large and small firms spanning all continents. Internet-enabled shared information helps break down organizational policies and functional fences, helping supply chain alliance members develop a common understanding of the competitive environment (Lambert & Cooper, 2016).

Information Systems researchers have mainly focused on the impact of IT on reducing coordination costs. This includes the cost of exchanging information and incorporating that information into decision processes as well as the cost incurred by the firm due to delays in the communication channel (Hayes et al. 2005). Within the context of transaction cost theory, this is a major component of transaction costs. However, the other major component, transaction risk, includes the risk of opportunistic behavior as well as the risk due to information asymmetry among the parties. One party could avoid responsibilities due to the inability of the other party to monitor. In addition, as indicated earlier, one party could take advantage of the relation-specific investments of the other. In addition to coordination cost, IT can reduce transaction risk by providing effective monitoring capabilities (Hayes et al. 2005).

Information systems refer to a system of interrelated components working together in order to collect, process, store and disseminate information to support decision-making, control and analysis in an organization (Fawcett & Magnan, 2012). The Internet can change the role and type of relationships between the various players, creating new value networks and developing a new business model (Schein, 2014). When information systems are used in managing the supply chain, conflicts may arise between organizations that are part of more than one supply chain, with varying strategic directions. These systems must fit within the organizational requirements of the supply chain members, or else the overall acceptance may not be adequate for the system's use (Sharafali, 2010). This is managed by cross-functional teams.

The supplier positioning model is a way that businesses rank their sources of supplies based on the amount of money spent with the supplier and the level of vulnerability a business has as if that supplier fails. According to (Huan, 2004), supplier positioning is a process of measuring spend or profit impact via volume purchased, the percentage of total cost and impact on product quality or business growth by supply risk via availability, number of suppliers, competitive demand, storage risks and substitution opportunities (Huan, 2004). Many large companies specify which suppliers are to be used by their first-tier suppliers, mainly because particular critical components have to fit with other critical components (Pitamber, 2014).

Supplier development is any activity undertaken by a purchaser to improve a supplier's performance or capabilities to meet the purchaser's short and long-term supply needs. Organizations rely on a variety of activities to improve supplier performance, including sharing technology, providing incentives, providing capital, and direct involvement of personnel with suppliers through activities such as training Krause and Handfield (2009). There is ample subjective evidence in corporate practice and academic research that supplier development helps improve supplier performance and or supplier capabilities (Krause et al., 2007). This helps them meet supply needs and generate favorable results for the buying firm. Recognizing the long-term and strategic benefits of supplier development, many companies have established supplier development programs and teams (Handfield, 2000).

The use of the Internet in business has become ubiquitous, and the arsenal of Internet-related tools to plan, organize and execute has substantially expanded. Pietersen (2012) conducted two consecutive studies on the adoption of e-business technologies in supply chain management – one in 1999 and the next in 2001. They found out that the difference of adopting such practices was abruptly grown only for two years. Given the fact that this research was carried out 10 years ago, I dare say that e-business technologies now play a crucial role in

managing business relations. As there exist a host of tools to facilitate supply chain integration, there is a need to ascertain in which integration contexts, they perform best. Such an investigation would have an important managerial implication. Despite that, it seems that this area is still under-researched.

Material and methods

The study adopted a descriptive survey design. The target population of the study was managers or equivalent from five (5) departments that is Procurement, finance, human resource, operations, and stores because they are directly concerned with the supply chain. According to records at the Portland, there are up to 1140 staffs within this departments, and this formed the target population. The sample of 92 respondents was used from the target population of 1140. The study used a questionnaire as the research instrument. The researcher also used Cronbach's Alpha to test the reliability of the proposed constructs. Qualitative and quantitative data were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. The same method was used to summarize the dependent variable as exhibited from the data collected from various investment clubs. Content analysis was used to analyze qualitative data. A regression model was used to establish the effect of various on Performance through supply chain practices, detailed in the conceptual framework. The dependent variable was continuous but modeled into logistic outcome as needed.

Multiple Regression Analysis Model

Performance at Portland was regressed against four variables as follows:

$$Y = a + B_1x_1 + B_2x_2 + \epsilon$$

Ys = Performance

a = Constant (Co-efficient of intercept)

X1 = Cost management ;

X2 = IT integration;

ε.= Error Term

B1B4= Regression co-efficient of four variables.

Findings And Discussion

The study distributed 92 questionnaires to the respondents.79 questionnaires out of the 92 were returned, which gives a response rate of approximately 85.87%. This response rate is above average. Even though the percentage rate of response was above average, the number of distributed questionnaires may have implications on the validity of the statistical analysis. The writer did, however, decide to continue with the analysis because the theoretical part of the project was already done.

Results of Pilot Study

A pilot study was carried out to determine the reliability of the questionnaires. Reliability analysis was subsequently done using Cronbach's Alpha which measures the internal consistency by establishing if certain items within a scale measure the same construct. Table 4.2 below shows that IT integration had the highest reliability ($\alpha=0.942$), followed by performance ($\alpha=0.915$), cost management was third ($\alpha=0.872$). This illustrates that all the five scales were reliable as their reliability values exceeded the prescribed threshold of 0.7. This, therefore, depicts that the research instrument was reliable and therefore required no amendments.

Descriptive Statistics and correlation

The overall mean response was 3.76 (SD = 0.667) indicating that the level of performance of cement manufacturing sector has improved. The findings in Table 1 show that cost management has a positive and significant relationship with the performance of cement manufacturing firms, $\rho = 0.712$, $p < 0.001$. Furthermore, the findings show that IT integration has a positive and significant relationship with the

performance of cement manufacturing firms, $\rho = 0.621$, $p < 0.001$. There are also significant inter-factor relationships that point to the fact that they are mutually dependent.

Table 1: descriptive and Correlation

	mean	Std deviation	Performance	Cost Management	It Integration
Performance	3.761	0.66797	1		
Cost management Information Communication Technologies	4.49	0.98	.712**	1	
	4.14	1.11	.621**	.609**	1

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Regression model

The findings in Table 2 on the model summary show that all the predictors explain 68.2% of the variation in performance of cement manufacturing firms ($R = 0.826$, R -squared = 0.682, Adjusted R -squared = 0.664). The coefficient of determination explains the extent to which changes in the response variable can be explained by the change in the explanatory variables or the percentage of variation in the dependent variable that is explained by all the independent variable. ANOVA results in Table 2 show that the model fit was good as illustrated by the overall test of significance with $F(4, 74)$ value of 39.607 with $p < 0.001$. Thus, the model was fit to the predIT performance of cement manufacturing firms based on cost management, IT integration, management support, lead time.

Effect of cost management on the performance of cement manufacturing firms

The specific objective of this study was to establish how cost management affect the performance of the cement manufacturing sector in Kenya. As such, the study sought to answer the following research question: To what extent does cost management affect the performance of the cement manufacturing sector in Kenya? The findings in Table 2 show that cost management does not have a significant effect on the performance of the cement manufacturing sector, $\beta_1 = 0.147$, $p = 0.188$. However, Krause et al., (2007) established that any effort of a buying firm to increase the performance and capabilities of the supplier and meet the buying firm's supply needs (Krause et al., 2007). Besides, Clemons et al. (2013) noted that cost management strategies take two forms and they can either be a result or process-oriented. In the case of result-oriented programs, they focus on costs, quality, and delivery.

Effect of IT integration on the performance of cement manufacturing sector

The second objective of this study was to determine how IT integration affect the performance of cement manufacturing sector in Kenya. The study aimed to answer the research question that: Does IT integration affect the performance of the cement manufacturing sector in Kenya? The findings in Table 2 show that IT integration has a positive and significant effect on the performance of cement manufacturing firms, $\beta_2 = 0.206$, $p = 0.017$. This means that with each unit increase in IT integration, performance increases by 0.206 units. In line with the results, Pietersen (2012) conducted two consecutive studies on the adoption of e-business technologies in supply chain management with the first study being undertaken in 1999 and the next in 2001. The author established that the difference of adopting such practices was abruptly grown only for two years.

Table 2: Regression model

	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		
	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.
(Constant)	0.639	0.263		2.43	0.018
cost management	0.126	0.095	0.147	1.328	0.188
IT integration	0.191	0.078	0.206	2.436	0.017
R Square	0.682				
Adjusted R Square	0.664				
F	39.607				
Sig.	0.000b				

a Dependent Variable: Performance

Conclusion

Basing on the study findings, cost management has no significant effect on the performance of cement manufacturing firms. It could be that the measures meant to improve the quality of suppliers has no influence on performance. There is, therefore, a need for further studies on the same to establish if the findings of the study hold.

Furthermore, IT plays a crucial role in enhancing the performance of cement manufacturing firms. Through IT firms can manage suppliers information in a more effective and efficient manner. Precisely, tools such as e-payment, it is easier for suppliers to make payments. Besides, IT facilitates interaction between the firm and suppliers. The eventual outcome is that IT improves the supply chain performance.

Recommendations

Since IT enhances the performance of cement manufacturing firms, firms should make use of IT to manage supplier information. Also, IT needs to be used to select suppliers and facilitate interaction with suppliers electronically. Furthermore, firms should allow their suppliers to use e-payment systems and have an integrated procurement management system. Instances of fraud in the tendering process can be reduced by posting tenders online and allowing all qualified supplier an equal opportunity of participation. This study recommends that another study is done to augment finding in this study. A comparative study across different industries might also be a more valuable contribution to this area of research. Moreover, the researcher has concluded that IT integration, top management supply support and lead time significantly relate to the performance of cement manufacturing firms, there is no evidence that performance is entirely dependent on the three independent variables. As such further research needs to be carried out to establish what other factors contribute significantly to performance of cement manufacturing firms.

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